

LITERATURE REVIEW ON ANIMAL IDIOMS: EXPLORING CULTURAL AND LINGUISTIC DIMENSIONS

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Annotation. This literature review examines animal idioms and proverbs' cultural and linguistic dimensions, exploring their role in reflecting societal norms, values, and human traits across languages. It investigates how animal idioms serve as metaphorical tools and cultural markers, highlighting universal patterns and culturally unique expressions. Through examples from English, Dargin, Mandarin Chinese, German, and Arabic, the study emphasizes the significance of animal idioms in language learning, cross-cultural communication, and symbolic thinking, showcasing their value as essential components of linguistic and cultural expression.

Keywords: animal symbolism, idiomatic expressions, cultural metaphors, linguistic diversity, zoonymic studies

Аннотация. Данное литературное обозрение исследует культурные и лингвистические аспекты зоонимических идиом и пословиц, акцентируя внимание на их способности отражать общественные нормы, ценности и черты характера человека в различных языках. Анализируя, как идиомы с использованием названий животных функционируют как метафорические инструменты и культурные маркеры, исследование выявляет как универсальные закономерности, так и культурно-специфические выражения. На примере английского, даргинского, китайского (мандарин), немецкого и арабского языков подчеркивается важность зоонимических идиом в изучении языка, межкультурной коммуникации и символическом мышлении, акцентируя их роль как неотъемлемых компонентов лингвистического и культурного выражения.

Ключевые слова: животная символика, идиоматические выражения, культурные метафоры, лингвистическое разнообразие, зоонимические исследования

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola hayvon nomlarini o'z ichiga olgan idiomalar va maqollarning madaniy va tilga oid jihatlarini o'rganadi. Maqolada hayvon nomlarini o'z ichiga olgan idiomalarning madaniy belgi va metaforaviy vosita sifatida qo'llanishi tahlil qilinib, ushbu hodisaning umumiy qonuniyatlari va o'ziga xos madaniy xususiyatlari yoritiladi. Ingliz, dargin, xitoy (mandarin), nemis va arab tillaridan keltirilgan misollar orqali idiomalarning til o'rganish jarayoni, madaniyatlararo muloqotdagi ahamiyati hamda ramziy tafakkurdagi roli ko'rsatilib, ularning til va madaniyatning ajralmas qismi sifatidagi o'rni alohida ta'kidlab o'tiladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: hayvon ramzlari, idiomatik ifodalar, metaforalar, lingvistik xilma-xillik, zoonimik tadqiqotlar

INTRODUCTION

Animal idioms and proverbs are significant in languages worldwide, serving as powerful tools for expressing human traits, emotions, and societal values through metaphorical associations. They enrich everyday communication and offer a window into the cultural and historical contexts that shape linguistic expressions. As an integral part of human life and imagination, animals have long been used as symbols to convey complex ideas, from bravery and wisdom to foolishness and deceit.

Studying animal idioms is essential for understanding how language reflects cultural perceptions and societal norms. These expressions often draw from universal observations of animal behavior, making them relatable across cultures while showcasing unique cultural attitudes. For instance, many cultures commonly associate the fox with cleverness, yet its symbolic nuances may vary, reflecting local values and beliefs. Proverbs, similarly, encapsulate collective wisdom and moral teachings, often using animals as a medium to convey their messages. Expressions like *“The early bird catches the worm”* or *“You can lead a horse to water, but you can’t make it drink”* not only impart lessons but also reveal the priorities and philosophies of the societies that created them. As language evolves, so does the symbolic use of animals, adapting to contemporary contexts while retaining traces of traditional values. However, the cultural specificity of these idioms poses challenges, particularly in crosslinguistic communication and translation, where their symbolic meanings may sometimes align with literal interpretations.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This literature review draws on the works of Adams, Thomas, and Kuder (1984), Collis (1994), Davies and Bentahila (1989), Gadzhalieva (2017), Hsieh (2006), Newmark (1988), Spears (1990), and Watson (1991). These key references provide diverse perspectives on animal idioms and proverbs, including their cultural significance, metaphorical usage, and pedagogical applications. The sources include idiomatic dictionaries, linguistic analyses, and cross-cultural studies, offering a

comprehensive foundation for examining the role of animal idioms across different languages and cultural contexts. Examples from English, Dargin, Mandarin Chinese, German, and Arabic were analyzed to explore universal patterns and culture-specific variations in animal-related expressions.

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

Adams, Thomas, and Susan Kuder explore how idioms influence attitudes and communication in their book “Attitudes through Idioms”. They emphasize idioms’ cultural and psychological significance in language learning, mainly focusing on how they reflect societal norms and values. A notable section of their work discusses animal-related idioms, highlighting their prevalence in everyday language due to the deep-rooted connections between humans and animals in culture and history. The authors explain that animal idioms often symbolize specific traits or behaviors attributed to their reference animals. For instance, “like a fish out of water” conveys discomfort or unfamiliarity, drawing on the biological reality of a fish’s dependence on water for survival. Adams emphasizes the pedagogical importance of teaching animal idioms in language learning, arguing that they enrich the vocabulary and provide insight into cultural mindsets. By understanding idioms such as “a wolf in sheep’s clothing” (a deceptive person), learners gain a deeper appreciation for the interplay between language, culture, and symbolic thinking.[1]

Gadzhaliyeva in her dissertation “The Person in the Zoonymic Worldview in Languages of Various Typologies (Based on Dargin, English, and Arabic Languages)”, examines how animal names (zoonyms) metaphorically represent human traits in Dargin, English, and Arabic. The study finds that zoonymic expressions often carry cultural significance, with Dargin showing a higher prevalence of negative connotations (e.g., turn “pig” for greed) compared to positive ones (e.g., Arslan “lion” for courage). In English, zoonyms like ass (donkey) convey foolishness, while others like bee represent industriousness. Arabic zoonyms like peacock symbolize pride, reflecting unique cultural associations.[5]

Across all three languages, fox, lion, and eagle universally denote positive traits, while donkey, snake, and pig carry negative meanings. Each language also features unique zoonotic terms:

- Dargin highlights bulls and mountain goats.
- English uses duck and magpie.
- Arabic emphasizes scorpion and ostrich.

Harry Collis, in *101 American English Proverbs*, offers a practical and engaging resource for understanding American culture through the lens of proverbs. Collis emphasizes that proverbs serve as a window into societal values, beliefs, and common wisdom, making them an essential tool for language learners and cultural enthusiasts. The book presents proverbs and explains their meanings, origins, and cultural contexts, ensuring readers grasp their significance in communication. Collis highlights proverbs' didactic and moral nature, which often convey lessons or advice succinctly.[2]

Davies and Bentahila, in their article “Familiar and Less Familiar Metaphors”, explore the use of metaphorical language across different cultures, emphasizing how metaphors reflect and shape cultural worldviews. Their study examines universal metaphors that resonate across cultures and those specific to individual societies, influenced by distinct cultural and linguistic frameworks. The authors highlight that metaphors often draw from shared human experiences, making some universally comprehensible. For example, metaphors related to animals, such as “strong as an ox” or “busy as a bee,” are common in multiple cultures due to universal observations of animal behavior. However, they note that the specific animals chosen and the traits they represent can vary, reflecting cultural priorities and perceptions. [3]

Shelly ChingYou Hsieh, in her article “A Corpus-Based Study on Animal Expressions”, examines how cultural perceptions influence the use and interpretation of animal-related expressions in Mandarin Chinese and German. Her corpus-based approach highlights idiomatic expressions' linguistic and cultural underpinnings, exploring how animals are metaphorically linked to specific traits in these two languages. Hsieh identifies how cultural values and societal beliefs shape the traits attributed to animals in idiomatic language. For instance, in Mandarin Chinese, the

term “laohu “ (tiger) is often associated with bravery, power, and authority, reflecting its symbolic importance in Chinese culture as a guardian figure and a representation of courage. Conversely, in German, foxes are commonly linked to cunning and cleverness, as seen in expressions like “schlau wie ein Fuchs” (clever as a fox), which mirrors the cultural perception of foxes as intelligent and strategic animals.[6]

Richard A. Spears, in “American Idioms Dictionary”, offers a comprehensive compilation of idiomatic expressions commonly used in American English. His work is precious for language learners, providing not only definitions but also examples and explanations of the context in which these idioms are used, making them accessible and practical for improving fluency and cultural understanding. Animal idioms like “let sleeping dogs lie” (to avoid stirring up trouble unnecessarily) and “straight from the horse’s mouth” (getting information directly from a reliable source) highlight how cultural perceptions of animals influence language. Spears notes that such idioms often reflect societal values and shared experiences, making them integral to effective communication.[8]

Donald Watson’s “Practicing Idioms” is a practical resource designed to help learners effectively integrate idiomatic expressions into their everyday speech. Watson emphasizes that mastering idioms is essential for fluency and sounding natural in conversational English. The book also addresses idioms involving animals, particularly prevalent in English. Watson provides examples such as “the lion’s share” (the most significant portion), “let the cat out of the bag” (to reveal a secret), and “raining cats and dogs” (heavy rain), breaking down their origins and cultural significance. He notes that these expressions often use vivid imagery to convey abstract ideas, making them memorable and impactful.[9]

Gadzhaliyeva explores the symbolic use of animal names in Dargin, English, and Arabic. She notes that *the lion* universally symbolizes courage, while *the donkey* often denotes foolishness across these languages. However, unique cultural associations exist, such as the Dargin *bull* symbolizing strength and the Arabic *peacock* representing pride. Hsieh highlights how cultural contexts influence idiomatic meanings, symbolizing bravery, and in German, reflecting shrewdness. These findings

demonstrate both universal and culture-specific patterns in animal idioms and convey lessons that resonate across cultures, though their exact phrasing and usage may differ. Newmark and Davies, Bentahila discuss the challenges of translating animal idioms due to cultural differences. For example, the English idiom “*a bull in a china shop*” requires an equivalent metaphor in other languages to convey its meaning effectively. The authors stress the need for cultural adaptation to preserve the idiom’s figurative essence.

CONCLUSION

Animal idioms bridge language and culture, offering insights into societal values and shared metaphors. While some idioms and proverbs have universal appeal, others reflect unique cultural perspectives. Understanding these expressions is essential for effective cross-cultural communication and language learning. Future research should explore the evolving use of animal idioms in contemporary contexts and their role in globalized communication. Animal idioms and proverbs offer profound insights into cultural values and linguistic creativity. Across languages, they serve as tools for teaching, communication, and cultural exchange. While some idioms and proverbs resonate universally, others are deeply rooted in specific cultural contexts, requiring careful interpretation and adaptation. This study highlights the importance of understanding animal-based idioms and proverbs in fostering cross-cultural competence and enriching language learning.

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